

PREVALENCE AND GENDER CHARACTERISTICS OF NON-ALCOHOLIC STEATOHEPATITIS IN THE CASE OF VALLEY POPULATION

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The purpose of the study is to determine the specific aspects of the spread, risk factors and course of non-alcoholic steatohepatitis in the conditions of the Fergana Valley, prediction and prevention.

The object of the study. A population of 476 (279 men, 197 women; 102 urban and 374 rural residents, 225 local and 251 foreign residents) patients with NStG of young, mature and elderly age were taken as subjects of the study.

Research methods. Epidemiological, general clinical, biochemical and instrumental methods (UTT, CT, MRI, Elastography, FGDS, ECG) and statistical methods were used in the research.

Scientific and practical significance of research results. The scientific significance of the research results is that the use of prospective epidemiological research methods in premorbid evaluation and diagnosis of non-alcoholic steatohepatitis, which is formed under the influence of various risk factors and pathological processes, in early detection and elimination, made it possible to accurately forecast its dosological status and stages of the disease process, as well as ways to properly organize pharmacocontrol. showed and confirmed.

The practical significance of the research results is that the application of the recommendations formed on the basis of the obtained results and the created technologies to practical activities (with their adaptation for all links of the health care organization) can lead to early detection of "internal" (within the liver) and "external" (outside the liver) complications observed in non-alcoholic steatohepatitis. Predicting and identifying in time specific prevention and safe pharmacotherapy measures have been achieved to reduce the "NStG continuum" (threatened liver failure, liver cirrhosis, liver tumor, death, re-hospitalization, reduced life expectancy), and to make the treatment safer.

Conclusions: 1). According to the 20-year epidemiological monitoring, the prevalence of non-alcoholic steatohepatitis in the elderly population of the

valley is 10.4%, with a significant difference, and it is confirmed that men (11.2%) prevail over women (9.4%). In the last 4 years, it has reached 4 times, representing a decreasing trend of 8.0% per year. 2). "Predictive-prophylactic algorithm and pharmacocontrol model of non-alcoholic steatohepatitis specific and significant for the Fergana Valley" developed on the basis of the research results, treatment-prophylaxis with medical (90.0%), economic (100.0%) and social (34.0%) results increases the quality of assistance.

